

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_3_1	
Title	<i>Google Earth Engine (GEE)</i>
Category	<i>Environmental/Spatial</i>
Purpose of the method	<i>We applied GEE in mapping baseline land use cover of Streedagh Beach, Ireland (CS 5).</i>
Effort in time	<i>2 weeks</i>
Number of objects investigated	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Marram grass cover</i> 2. <i>Sand dunes cover</i> 3. <i>Other covers</i>
Data format	<i>Geospatial/ images</i>
Description	<p><i>GEE hosts a lot of geospatial data, including regularly updated satellite and climate datasets. It facilitates processing datasets through user written scripts to analyze and visualize data directly on the platform and output results stored in the Google cloud and downloadable for further analysis and visualization in other geospatial tools. In our context Machine Learning land use cover classification of Streedagh Special Area of Conservation with Sentinel 2 satellite image for 09/2024. GEE makes available several variables that can be measured including land/habitat cover and their changes (e.g. marram grass cover), water (e.g. ocean water extent) and Climate. The results Interpretation would be guided by the objective of the analysis. In our context temporal cover changes from baseline to future i.e. the changes in marram grass cover at the start of behavioral change campaigns to a future time to assess the status of influencing beach users in reducing the grass degradation hence the dunes erosion. This is feeds to informing policy on ecosystem and biodiversity conservation.</i></p>
Basic Literature	<p><i>Gorelick, N., Hancher, M., Dixon, M., Ilyushchenko, S., Thau, D., & Moore, R. (2017). Google Earth Engine: Planetary-scale geospatial analysis for everyone. Remote Sensing of Environment. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2017.06.031</i></p> <p><i>Parracciani, C., Gigante, D., Mutanga, O., Bonafoni, S., & Vizzari, M. (2024). Land cover changes in grassland landscapes: Combining enhanced Landsat data composition, LandTrendr, and machine learning classification in google earth engine with MLP-ANN scenario forecasting. GIScience & Remote Sensing, 61(1), 2302221.</i></p> <p><i>Sunde, M., Diamond, D., & Elliott, L. (2024). Ecological Systems Classification: Integrating Machine Learning, Ancillary Modeling, and Sentinel-2 Satellite Imagery. Remote Sensing, 16(23), 4440.</i></p>

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Linked material	https://code.earthengine.google.com/ https://code.earthengine.google.com/b619d460d55f2f0c4ccdada2fff01e8b6 https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1UDVYfPGKiVn0T9HV2VbALqRzJVwvbUN?usp=drive link